

ONLINE VIRAL VIDEOS: A STUDY ON CONSUMERS' PERCEPTIONS AND INFLUENCE

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to investigate the characteristics that make a video "viral" and lead to its promotion as well as to examine the impact that viral videos have on consumers' online behaviour. Qualitative research was conducted on a sample of 11 people through in-depth interviews. The main findings of the research revealed that pleasant emotions seem to lead consumers promoting or not promoting a video. Branding and the participants' perceptions also played an important role in their promoting corporate videos. However, their perception about brands did not seem to be easily influenced by brand viral videos. The difficulty of influencing participants continues in terms of the degree of promotion of viral videos in relation to the perceived effect, the perceived social pressure, and the perceived control of their behaviour. Companies should focus their efforts together to multiple different social media platforms where consumers are active and should not underestimate the value of viral videos in terms of promoting their products and services.

Keywords: viral videos, viral marketing, brand augmentation, social media, sharing videos, online consumer behaviour

Introduction

With the current rapid technological development, viral marketing combined with social media are creating new ways of communication and exchange of information between marketers and consumers. This information comes in the form of simple texts and links, such as on Facebook and Twitter, in the form of photos, such as on Instagram, but also in the form of videos and music tracks, such as on YouTube and TikTok. Many of the social media platforms combine the above media forms, such as Facebook. Other social media are very well targeted, such as LinkedIn. Some authors have suggested (Abdullah, 2016; Strandberg & Styvén, 2020) that word of mouth (WOM) and buzz can take place in the real world, but WOM has presently transformed to taking place electronically via the Internet, and especially through social media. However, as Buttle and Groeger (2017) argued, offline WOM activity may create an important value for a brand since the biggest part of WOM activity takes place in the real world. Karr (2015) added that viral marketing attempts to transmit marketing content that spreads rapidly and significantly between consumers. Denisova (2020) took the same definition approach when mentioning that ‘viral’ is a substandard term for information that can rapidly spread. Despite the range of content that is shared online, viral marketing has mainly been studied in terms of marketing and advertising, so it has been limited to commercially oriented content. Also, while the majority of research has targeted viral marketing in relation to e-mails, online communities, and marketplaces, the present research deals with viral videos whether or not they have been created for commercial purposes and studies the characteristics that create the conditions for their going viral. In this study, the effect of viral videos on Greek consumers’ online behaviour is studied through the theory of pre-planned behaviour

(Theory of Planned Behaviour). Consumers' intentions to promote a viral video through social media are investigated as well as the factors that make a video “viral.”

Theoretical Approach - The Concept of Viral Marketing and Viral Video

Viral marketing can be defined as marketing actions, activities, institutions, and processes that have value for customers, consumers, and society and that have been caused by an electronic "virus" since their reputation spreads and multiplies just like a virus (Rodrigues and Fonseca, 2016). Based on the analyses of Armstrong and Kotler (2009), Strandberg and Styvén (2020), Xiaofang (2012), Rodrigues and Fonseca (2016) and Sprong (2010) it is understood that in viral marketing users or consumers have a particularly important role. Companies and organizations, on the other hand, are looking for the medium, product, or service through which they will bring consumers closer to the market to transmit marketing messages at a very low cost, with widespread properties and immediate distribution. The origins of viral marketing can be traced back to 1996-1997 when Tim Draper persuaded Hotmail, a start-up e-mail provider company at the time, to insert at the end of each email that Hotmail users sent a promotional line with a clickable URL prompting the recipient to register to their service. (Haryani, & Motwani, 2015; Xiaofang, 2012; Abedniya & Sabbaghi, 2010; Sprong 2010; Xavier & Summer, 2009; Fairbank, 2008; Cruz & Fill, 2008). Many researchers have claimed that the anticipated outcome of viral marketing is online WOM communication (Cruz & Fill, 2008; Hendrayati & Pamungkas, 2020). They have also noted that WOM refers to the face-to-face communication that consumers have and refers to their experience regarding a product or service. Viral marketing can be found through various forms on the Internet, such as video-clips, mini-sites (Reichstein & Bruschi, 2019), photos, and images

(Hendrayati & Pamungkas, 2020), online games, interactive websites, and e-mail, according to Sprong (2010) and based on Van der Lans et al. (2010) and Sjerps (2009). According to researchers like Tucker (2015) and Broxton et al. (2011), viral videos are video clips that users spread through the Internet and that become widely known through various social networking sites, such as YouTube, Facebook, Snapchat, Instagram, TikTok, etc. Yang and Wang (2015) argued that what characterizes a video as viral is how many people share this video in relation to how many people watch it in total and not how many times it has been watched. One of the largest online platforms for video playback and promotion is YouTube, with millions of daily visitors around the world. YouTube has a unique algorithm system to recommend videos to users and to help make a video become viral. Multiple criteria are processed, such as the watch time. If a user has watched a video completely or partially, YouTube also captures implicit feedback (Abbas, et al., 2017).

Emotions as the Motivation for Promoting Online Content of Social Media Users

According to Heath (1996), people prefer to promote and share with other people information that does not contain purely the element of surprise, and it may have positive or negative content. Baños et. al. (2020), concluded that there is a tendency to promote videos that have a strong positive content, therefore videos that create positive emotions or that are deeply fixed in the mind are more viral than those that create negative emotions. Izawa (2010) reported that, based on research conducted by Peters et al. in 2009 on 160 students, people tended to share information that was interesting and that contained the elements of surprise, disgust, and joy. Also, Hayes and King (2014), Teixeira (2012), and Jenkins (2011) agreed that emotions are a significant factor for promoting or not promoting some information in videos.

Motivation to Promote Online Content

Bruyn and Lilien (2008) argued that people forward emails for many reasons and one of them is for recreational purposes as well as for social networking reasons. Palka et al. (2009) presented information about people who promote videos based on how interesting or useful the information might be to the receiver, including information such as what impact such a move would have on their reputation, if it is a good move to express and to stay in touch with others, if the content they would promote is enjoyable but also if the content they intended to promote had something to do with the recipient. Furthermore, according to Dafonte (2014), language does not prove to be a barrier for videos to become viral; on the contrary, the promotion of a video can happen regardless of its language. In addition, Syn and Oh (2015) concluded that learning and social engagement are the key motivations that encourage people to share information online, while personal gain is considered to be the least influential factor. Since personal gain is the weakest motivation, this could result in a smaller likelihood for users to contribute information for their personal benefit and instead to share information that satisfies their need for communication and relationship enhancement. Furthermore, knowledge about a topic and mutuality are significant motives for users to share information online.

The Impact of Information and Motivation on Advertising

According to Sabri (2017), viral content weakens the taboo perceptions of a provocative advertising message and encourages purchases. Also, users share provocative advertising with their friends when they believe they will approve of it and will not be shocked. In addition to

previous research, the findings of Gopal (2021) suggested that surprise and the perceived shock impact from an ad are key factors for users to share an advertising message. Users are more likely to share advertising content that surprises them and is not conceived as shocking. Teixeira (2012) noted that there are two very important categories of incentives for promoting content by consumers: altruistic motives for the recipients' benefit and egocentric motives for personal gain. In addition, he concluded that the video content that people share plays a very important role as they usually choose to share entertainment and general information.

Southgate et al. (2010) found that the rules that apply to successful video TV commercials, also apply to viral videos, such as the participation of celebrities and the use of music as a means of evoking emotions.

The Effects of Viral Video on Brand Augmentation through Social Media

Social media is a powerful tool for promoting content for companies, but also a powerful tool for filtering content for users (Qualman, 2009). Nielsen found in his 2012 study that consumers spent a very significant portion of their time online using social media and therefore he suggested that companies and advertisers use these avenues to share their messages. On all continents, social media has the potential to influence consumers' purchasing decisions in many product and service categories, making such platforms a valuable tool for companies to create positive consumer impressions with the prospect of increasing their sales. With this data, companies are moving to viral video transmission, which, according to Eckler and Bolls (2011), offers more incentives for promotion and evokes more emotion than does traditional advertising, be it pleasant or unpleasant or motivating. Teixeira (2012), in a study conducted at Harvard

University, stated that viral videos created by brands, or viral ads, are the cornerstone of e-marketing as many viewers share these videos with family and friends. However, according to Prajogo (2020), as long as the advertisement has a high viral intent and receives positive acceptance, it will have an increased likelihood of consumers' purchasing and an intensified level of brand awareness. Advertising messages including humour and informative characteristics tend to have a positive and significant impact on viral intention.

Online Consumer Behaviour - Theory of Planned Behaviour

According to Bi et al. (2019), one of the accepted principles in consumer behaviour is that WOM, especially through video (vWOM) has a crucial impact in shaping consumer habits and behaviour. Of course, before consumers make the decision to buy a product or service, they must obtain the necessary information (Baubonienė & Gulevičiūtė, 2015). Searching for information on the Internet about a product or service can be done by browsing through product-related pages or through social media where consumers interact not only with the "pages" of companies but also with friends and relatives. In addition, the videos that consumers watch contain a wealth of information, which they can later process and evaluate.

The literature contains various models of interpretation of consumer behaviour. More specifically, Ajzen (1991) developed the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), which involves linking consumers' attitudes to their behaviours. Using three key variables, Ajzen sought to clarify individuals' intentions to adopt a behaviour and found three criteria: (1) consumers' attitude towards a behaviour, which refers to the positive or negative assessment they have about a behaviour; (2) the subjective norms and standards (subjective norms), which refers to the

perception of the pressure that consumers receive from society regarding the execution of a behaviour; and (3) the perception of behavioural control (perceived behavioural control), which refers to the perception of the ease or difficulty of performing a behaviour, which also includes factors from past experiences.

Research Methodology

Qualitative Research - Process Description

The two objectives of the present research are the study of the characteristics of viral videos that contribute to their promotion and the influence that viral videos have on Greek consumers' online behaviours. The above objectives were studied through qualitative research by conducting in-depth interviews.

Concluding from above literature, below research questions were formed:

RQ1: Are users motivated to promote a viral video?

RQ2: Does the brand affect the degree to which the consumer watches and promotes a viral video?

RQ3: Do viral videos affect consumers' perceptions of brands?

RQ4: Do the factors of Theory of Planned Behaviour influence the promotion of a viral video by a consumer?

As social media is an integral part of the research, the invitation to participate in the interview process was made through Facebook to a number of people who are very active in this specific social network in terms of watching and sharing videos, and who are working and living in Athens, Greece. The choice of Facebook to find the interviewees was made as Facebook is the most popular social network in Greece and its members are very active in terms of watching and

promoting videos within it (Kemp, 2021). Each interview had a different location as the researcher gave the interviewees the freedom to select a place to ensure that the environment would be familiar to them and that they would not need to spend time finding the location.

Out of the 15 candidates, 11 responded positively. A total of 11 interviews were conducted with an average duration of 20 minutes. With the permission of the interviewees, the interviews were recorded, transcribed, and analysed by the researcher. Prior to the start of the recording, the researcher informed the interviewees about the objectives and purposes of the research, the recording of the interview, and the importance of the research.

Data Collection Process

The following questions were used as a collection tool for data:

1. What do you know about the term “viral video”?
2. Why do you think makes a video become so popular that it goes viral?
3. What is your opinion about viral videos used by companies as a promotional tool?
4. Under what conditions would you watch a promotional video promoted by an acquaintance?
5. Write down the reasons that you would enter the process of promoting a promotional video to your acquaintances via the Internet.
6. Describe a case in the past when you saw such a video and consider how it affected you as a consumer, either positively or negatively.
7. What characteristics do you think a video should have in order to influence your consumer habits and change your view about a brand?

8. What features on a corporate viral video do you believe can influence your purchasing habits?

Cluster Analysis

Clustering analysis was performed both based on the sources (i.e. the eleven interviews) and based on the nodes (i.e. the interview groups based on the respondents' genders and age groups). Out of the 11 respondents, nine were men and two were women. While a total of four respondents were between 20 and 24 years old, four were between 25 and 29 years old, and another three were 30 years old or older.

The choice of cluster analysis was made to confirm through the program any categorization or grouping of the collected data, based on the characteristics of the sample that participated in the research process.

In the following analysis, the term "sources" is used to describe the data sources, i.e., our sample, while the term "nodes" is used to describe the nodes of the system, i.e., the sample groups based on their demographics characteristics. Regarding the interviews, grouping was performed based on the coding of the data and based on the similarity of the words each participant used. The grouping was based on the Pearson correlation coefficient. Two central groups emerged, one with women and one with men. The men's group was also divided into three subgroups, based on their ages (20–24, 25–29, and 30 or older).

Regarding the grouping based on the similarity of words in the interviews, two central groups emerged, one of which consisted of six men and the other of three men and the two women.

Regarding the nodes, grouping was performed based on the data coding, which was based on the similarity of the words used by each participant, but also on the characteristics of the groups. In both cases, here also the grouping was based on the Pearson correlation coefficient.

In terms of grouping with coding, two central groups emerged, one with women aged 25 to 29 years old, and one with the remaining nodes. It also turned out that all of those who belonged to the age group of 30 and older were men.

Respectively, regarding the grouping based on the similarity of words, two central groups clearly emerged, one of which consisted of men aged 20—24 years old and 30 or older, while the other was of women aged 25—29 years old, which shows that to a large extent, the two genders seemed to use different terminology.

Finally, regarding the grouping based on the characteristics, two central groups emerged, one of which concerned age, and the other concerned gender.

In-depth Interview Analysis

Question 1: What do you know about the term “viral video”?

Regarding the first question, most of the respondents had heard the term “viral video” but did not know exactly what it meant. Characteristically, one of them stated, "I guess it has to do with videos that are on the Internet, and you can either be informed or asked for something through them." Another said, "I have definitely heard it but I am not sure what exactly it means." Many also associated the term with YouTube, with one participant pointing out that "[the] definition I

would give is videos that encourage those who watch them to share with their friends and in their turn with their own friends and so on... until many people find out about it in a very short time.”

Another respondent directly linked it to humour and high traffic: “A video that has a lot of views, which in a way affects, even for a short time, the culture. Many people recognise this video, and it influences with humour or with a message it transmits. It has caught our attention.”

Question 2: *Why do you think makes a video become so popular that it goes viral?*

Respondents were then asked to express their views on why such a video would be so popular. The views expressed included, to a general extent, originality and humour. One respondent said, "One reason is when it is very funny or...basically if it has something special. That means being funny, weird, and generally special.” Making the video funny is something that was mentioned by more than half of the respondents. Apart from that, another one said, "...they usually have something original, and it is a bit more extreme,” while another participant gave a different dimension, emphasizing that "... for various cases I have heard, some have somewhat strange content—humiliating a person or mocking in general."

Question 3: What is your opinion about viral videos used by companies as a promotional tool?

Almost all participants knew that this type of video is also used by companies for advertising purposes. Most of them did not have a problem with the specific use, while some others set some restrictions. One participant stated that his feeling of liking such a video depended on the company: “If it is a bank, I do not like it. You want to make fun of us and waste our money (irony) at the same time. If it is some other kind of company for which I have a neutral or a good opinion,

then I watch the video, I laugh, and I say that ‘at least they spent some of their time and made something funny.’ I consider it as positive." However, only one respondent seemed to be opposed to the use of corporate videos: "No [I do not agree] because it affects one’s mental world and does not help [people] see what [they] really need and what [they do] not.

Question 4: Under what conditions would you watch a promotional video promoted by an acquaintance?

The conditions under which the participants would watch a viral video were examined, as well as the importance they attributed to a video if it was promoted by an acquaintance. Most of them said they would rather watch such a video, but some pointed out that if the video were promotional or from a company, they probably would not watch it. In any case, it is clear from the answers that if the video were suggested by a friend or acquaintance, this would be a motivational factor to watch it, and almost all participants agreed on this. Characteristically, one of them said, "I would trust it and watch it more readily," while another responded, "Yes, if my friends suggested it to me, I would watch it." However, some were more sceptical: "I filter the people who promote videos. I know that just because someone bothered to send me a video, that doesn’t mean it will be good. So, if certain people promote it to me, I watch it directly. There is the opposite case of course."

Question 5: Write down the reasons that you would enter the process of promoting a promotional video to your acquaintances via the Internet.

It is particularly important regarding a viral video to know if a user will go through the process of promoting it. Most of the participated emphasized that they would promote such a video if they liked it or if they found it interesting or successful. Only a few expressed some doubts. For example, one said they would "only if it was a pre-request to win something," and another stated that he would do it "only if it did not have to do with direct commercial activity." In general, there was a feeling that most of the participants would promote such a video as long as it was funny or interesting.

Question 6: Describe a case in the past when you saw such a video and consider how it affected you as a consumer, either positively or negatively.

Almost all participants reported a case in the past when they had seen a corporate viral video and it affected their view of the company positively or negatively. Videos by Apple, Intel, Coca-Cola, and Volkswagen were mentioned. In most cases, the videos had a positive effect on the respondents, except for one case where it was emphasized that there was a negative impact. The participant explained that he had seen a "nice video but I did not like the way it was promoted. She [spokesperson in video] was promoting herself through it. He mentioned the name of the company many times and emphasized 'look what we did.'"

Question 7: What characteristics do you think a video should have in order to influence your consumer habits and change your view about a brand?

Equally important about viral videos is whether such a video drives the consumer to seek more information about the company and the product. It seems that more than half of the

respondents have entered into such a process in the past, while the rest did not. One respondent said, "I liked some Cosmote [a Greek telecommunication provider] ads that asked for volunteers. I searched to see how I could help, and I searched on their site various things related to their social work." Another participant reported a video about Old Spice, while other participants reported videos about video games, cars, and a bank. Four of the participants stated that they had never been through such a process.

Question 8

What features on a corporate viral video do you believe can influence your purchasing habits?

Finally, respondents were asked to identify some common features in corporate viral videos that affected their consumer habits. Something that is widely reported by many consumers is the emotion they felt and how they related with the video. One of them stated that "they [corporate videos] promote the feeling a lot. They make you relate with the video." In the same context, another participant said, "You may decide to buy something because of the emotions and not because you need it," while another participant said, "Generally these days is common practice to provoke positive emotions, like Coca Cola. Even when you show something negative but with the ultimate aim to fight a situation, like violence against women." Another feature that seemed to be emphasized by consumers was humour. One of them said, "Most (videos) are funny, impressive and smart," while another accordingly stated that "... if it is smart, funny or cool and manages these elements properly." Finally, two participants mentioned as a special feature the ability of the video to keep the viewer watching until the end without making them lose interest.

Concluding for above responses, regarding RQ1 it can be understood that users are motivated to promote videos and convert them to viral. Many responders would promote a video if it had some characteristics, like it was funny, weird or special and original in general.

Additionally, as reported from above concerning RQ2 the brand does not seem to affect the degree to which consumers watch viral videos. The majority of the responders mentioned that they have watched videos produced by brands and some of these they liked them too. Also, in some cases they were motivated to learn more details about the brand.

Consequently, regarding RQ3, undeniably all participants had watched a video about a brand and it affected their perception either positively or negatively. In most cases though, there was a positive impact created by the viral video to the responders.

Finally concerning RQ4 it can be understood from the reported replies, factors of Theory of Planned Behaviour do influence the promotion of a video. Some responders would not watch a video if they had previously formed in their mind an unpleasant perception about the presented product or brand. Additionally, if the concept of the video was related to social norms i.e. anti-violence, they would be intrigued to watch it.

Conclusions

One of the main conclusions of this analysis concerns factors that may influence a consumer to promote a viral video. The emotions evoked by video content have been found to affect consumer behaviour. More specifically, surprise, branding, and pleasant emotions are factors that lead to the promotion of a viral video. This finding is largely related to research by Sabri (2017) who stated that people prefer to promote and share with other people information that

does not strongly contain the element of surprise, which in part contradicts the results. of the present investigation.

In contrast, according to a 2009 study conducted by Peters et al., 160 students were interviewed about their willingness to share stories that may or may not be true. They found that their participants tended to share information that was interesting, including the element of surprise, disgust, and joy, which was confirmed by the results of the present research.

This conclusion was also confirmed by Jenkins (2011) who noted that the role of emotions in the decision that a consumer is called to make regarding the dissemination of information or not is particularly important and cannot be ignored. The emotions that are created in viewers when watching an ad are the ones that will lead them to either share the ad or change their opinion about a brand (Jenkins, 2011), which was confirmed in this study.

Similarly, the results of the research by Teixeira (2012), who mentioned that viral videos created by brands, or viral ads, are the cornerstone of e-marketing as a large number of people share these videos with family and friends. In contrast, Freistad and Wright (1994) described the Persuasion Knowledge Model, according to which, through a continuous process, people, through their experiences, communicate with others and watch ads to gain knowledge about how, why, and when a message is meant to influence them. The above model is an obstacle for marketers. Through this, consumers essentially filter each brand's intentions. Freistad and Wright (1994) wrote, "We generally believe that people do not use persuasion knowledge to resist the messages they receive. They mostly use it to manage / control and filter the content they share with others." Therefore, companies are called to create content that has value for users and that conveys their corporate

messages in such a way that users want to share it with their own circle of contacts and ultimately shape their consumer behaviour based on this—something that is neither given nor easy to achieve.

Based on the results of the present study, the factors of the theory of planned behaviour, i.e., the perceived result, the perceived "social pressure," and the perceived control, do not affect consumers' degree of promotion of a viral video. However, this result does not apply to the whole population, as it seemed that the men participants paid more attention to social pressure and less importance to perceptual control, and the younger participants generally paid more attention to the factors of the theory of pre-planned behaviour.

In general, it is clear that the emotions that develop from the information we share play an important role in our decision to promote or not to promote some information. The fact that the emotions caused by these videos seemed to be particularly important, in terms of whether or not consumers will promote them, means that companies should pay special attention to this area in order to achieve the best promotion of their products through such videos.

It is also clear that attention should be focused not only on YouTube, but also on other social media, such as Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok, through which it appeared that users are largely promoting such videos.

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